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PERSPECTIVES OF INNOVATIVE TENDENCIES IN TOURISM AS AN IMPORTANT OF PREPARATION ON SPECIALISTS OF «SERVICES SECTOR»

The integration process at the corresponding stages is to implement European norms and standards in education, tourism, distribution of native cultural and scientific–technical achievements in the European Union. Eventually, such steps will work on increase the European cultural identity in Ukraine and integration to European intellectual, educational and scientific and technical environment. The management of the State Tourism Administration of Ukraine sees one of the significant steps in the development of the industry in controlling the quality of tourist services provided to the client [1, p. 60].

The Ukrainian Innovation Development Strategy for 2010–2020 years, in the context of globalization trends and modern challenges, Ukrainian higher education should professionally prepare people for life in the information society, society of knowledge and innovation, to form a person with innovative thinking, innovative culture, and ability to innovate activity, which becomes a guarantee of the competitiveness of the national economy [5]. All of these requirements directly affect the process of professional preparation for tourism.

Creation of a new educational system, adapted to the dynamic changes, taking place in tourism in the conditions of an innovative economic formation, has a priority task in most European countries. As you know, tourism is a unique kind of activity; it is characterized by globalization, sustainable development and positive economic results. Globalization, the growth of tourist flows put of new requirements for tourism education: the availability of the only professional qualifications of tourism activity, knowledge of foreign languages, culture, and economics, legal and social systems of partner–countries.

The World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), which supports education, conducts educational programs for tourism, a significant role in solving the problem of preparation specialists are played. In last years, identification has emerged in the field of tourism and in the preparation of specialists system with a large number of specializations that reflect the diversity of tourist services and take into account the prospects for rapid development of the industry.

Today in Ukraine there are about 3 thousand enterprises that have received licenses for tourism activities. According to official figures, 75% of them are engaged in tourist activities in a part–time. That is, from time to time, and the image of Ukraine on the world tourist market depends on the quality of the tourist product (services) offered by tourist enterprises (firms), and not on their quantity. Quality of activity (service) depends from professionalism, qualification, experience of personnel of tourist enterprises (firms).

In order to change Ukraine into a world-class tourist country, it is necessary to ensure coordination of the activities of the economic sectors on which the quality provision of tourist services depends. It is a hotel industry, transport, trade, communication, etc.

Another important motive for the arrival of foreign tourists to Ukraine is the natural resources and historical-cultural heritage of our country. The cost of natural resources and historical-cultural monuments depends on their availability and qualitative characteristics. Depending on the degree of accessibility of these resources and their exploitation for the purpose of tourism, they will become of great economic importance for Ukraine [6, p. 21].

The activation of the tourism services sector necessitates the development and implementation of a quality management system (QMS) as an integral part of the development strategy of tourism in general and at the level of its individual enterprises. The most realistic way to achieve this goal is formation of a mechanism of state regulation and management of the quality of tourist services, which should be directed at the comprehensive, purposeful using of measures, systems and management methods [3].

In the tourist-excursion business in Ukraine, a long time monopolized the state and customers had to put up with what they offered. Today, the situation is changing, and there are numerous private tourism companies, which are still mainly engaged in the organization of foreign travel. But not far off is the time when foreigners are attracted to Ukrainian routes. In these circumstances, healthy competition plays a positive role, which will force tour companies to set up their business in order to have regular customers and to do so provide them with high-quality and diverse services, taking into account the diverse tastes and cultural and aesthetic needs of consumers.

Management of the quality of tourist services should be carried out systematically, that is, at the enterprises – subjects of the tourist industry should operate a system of quality management of tourist services. Such a system is an organizational structure with a clear distribution of responsibilities, procedures, processes and resources that are needed to manage the quality of a tourist product. World experience has formed not only general features of existing quality management systems, but also principles and methods that can be applied in each of them [2, p. 125]. There are three types of quality control systems that have conceptual differences: systems that meet the requirements of ISO 9000 series standards: General Quality Management Systems (TQM – Total Quality Management); systems that meet the criteria for national or international (regional) awards, diplomas in quality of service sector.

The life cycle of services includes all stages of its existence: from the initial definition of requirements and needs of the consumer to their ultimate satisfaction. The life cycle according to ISO 9004: 2009 is schematically provided by a loop or quality spiral [7]. Thus, when managing the quality of travel services, it is advisable to distinguish between «quality assurance», «quality management» and «quality improvement» in accordance with ISO 9001: 2008 [3].

Quality Assurance is a set of planned and systematic measures necessary to ensure that the service meets certain quality requirements. Quality Control (Quality Control) is a coordinated effort to direct and monitor the organization's performance in relation to quality [3]. Typically, quality management is represented by a system of methods and measures that are implemented to meet quality requirements. Of course, this concept is recommended to be used with refinement definitions such as Quality Management in Manufacturing (Manufacturing Quality Control) or Quality Management at Company Level (Company – Wide Quality Control).

Quality management includes methods and activities of operational nature, aimed at simultaneously managing the process and eliminating the reasons for poor functioning at the appropriate stages of quality.

The General Quality Management (Quality Management) is a component of a general management function that defines and ensures a quality policy. This management function includes: operational planning, resource allocation, and other systematic actions in the field of quality, such as quality planning, performance and performance evaluation.

The system of quality management in the process of implementation and improvement organically interacts with other social and industrial systems of enterprises of the tourism industry. First and foremost, it is the management of the development of a tourism product (routes, tours), production planning, technological training, material and financial resources, quality of work, training, etc. Taken together, these systems cover all sectors of the labour collective of the tourist enterprise: production, economic, social, and technological.

Achievement of the efficiency of the quality management system at the enterprises of the tourism industry can not be achieved without the use of various innovative forms and the active influence of the service and management personnel on improving the quality of service of tourists, travel agents and counterparties:

1. *Implementation of innovations* (organizational innovations) that are related to the development of entrepreneurship and tourism business in the system and management structure, including reorganization, absorption of competing subjects on the basis of new technology and advanced technologies, personnel policy, rational economic and financial activities;
2. *Marketing innovations*, its can meet the needs of target customers, or attract new customers;
3. *Periodic innovations* (food innovations) aimed at changing the consumer qualities of a tourism product, its positioning on the market.

Today, the most important characteristic of innovation is its novelty, which promotes: the expansion of the range of potential consumers (tourists); change of pounds of consumer and expansion of function tourist product [6, p. 21].

Innovation in tourism should include, first of all, those innovations that are accompanied by: restore and development of spiritual and physical forces of tourists; qualitatively new changes in tourist products; increase in the

efficiency of the tourism infrastructure; increase of efficiency of management of sustainable operation and development of tourist sphere in the country; increase of efficiency of processes of formation, positioning and consumption of tourist services; progressive changes in the factors of production; increase of image and competitiveness of enterprises of the tourist industry.

The large automation and internalization of the information space of the society reveals the horizons of attractive resorts, places for recreation and stimulates consumers to independently choose the route of travel, search for affordable services at the lowest prices and provide proactive communication with service providers, which translates the business of tourist organizers into the virtual sector.

This sector of travel, backed by the achievements of the Internet–industry, ensures the functioning of the network information space, especially in travel agency for the sale of bundled offers (tour operator and travel agency).

The most powerful Internet–sector of sales operates with the capabilities of electronic booking systems, promotion and sales of travel services. Information support for such process innovations are: Global Distribution System (GDS), a combination of powerful professional booking and reservation systems for all types of travel services (Amadeus, Galileo, Worldspan, Travelport, Saber, Serena; Alternative Distribution System (ADS) – alternative booking systems that are created as price aggregators and offer the possibility to book both package tours and individual services for intermediaries or direct clients (portals such as booking.com, expedia.com, tickets.ua, hotels.com., lastminute.com., ORBITZ and other online booking sites for travel services for end users and agencies); Central Reservation System (CRS) – centralized reservation system for solving electronic distribution problems. This highly–technological development is a marketing innovation and is intended for downloading information on hotel services (airlines, tour operators, etc.) into all existing electronic channels of sale in order to increase the efficiency of direct online sales from the site of the company.

The further development of the virtualization of the tour is directed at the widespread use of mobile technologies by tourists before, during and after the trip, as well as with the aim of finding the necessary information about the special offers of tour operators, contact information, taking part in the prize draw, additional tour services, etc.

Conclusions. Also, the new directions of using information technologies for tourism are: introduction of mobile Internet, electronic catalog of offers; distribution of online booking not only in working with retail agencies, but also directly with customers; fullness of sites for information on countries and new tourist routes, software and software solutions – these are just a few examples illustrating the innovative activity of tourism enterprises and the areas of its further development. The above trends require consumers to have some experience in travel, knowledge about the use of mobile and Internet technologies, as well as the high professional level of personnel of tourist intermediary organizations.

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